

Implementation and Assessment of Task Based Learning (TskBL) Strategy in Preclinical Education

Roopashree Shenoy, Animesh Jain, Bhagyalakshmi K, Arun Shirali, Sneha B Shetty, Anand Ramakrishna, Rashmi KS

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 13, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 15, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Task Based Learning, Early Clinical Exposure, Standardized Patient Encounter, Medical Education, Preclinical Learning</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5573184</p>	<p><i>Preclinical Task based learning is a simulated learning approach in which focus for students is a real task done by a medical professional using a standardized patient encounter. Our study aimed at planning, implementing and assessing task based learning for topic diabetes mellitus among first year medical students and comparing it to conventional method of tutorials in physiology MBBS curriculum. Participants (n=250) were divided into a task based learning group (n=84) and a tutorial (n=166) group. The task based learning group was further divided into smaller groups of 14 students and underwent standardised patient encounter (one hour). In this session, they elicited history from the standardised patient, analysed laboratory results and provided patient education relevant to patient's condition. At the end they prepared a sequential case summary. After a gap of one week they underwent the discussion session (two hours) in which they presented the case summary and discussed the learning objectives relevant for the task. The tutorial learning group was divided into smaller groups of 28 students and they underwent one session that took place for two hours duration. In this session the students discussed in their respective groups (5-6 students) and answered the case based questions provided by the facilitator. Formative assessment was done using facilitator feedback for both the groups. The task based learning group also received standardized patient feedback. Summative assessment was done using Pre and post-test assessments. They were conducted using the Multiple Choice Question (MCQ) test and Objective structured clinical examinations (OSCE). The mean task based learning scores for MCQ and OSCE were significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) than the tutorial group. Pre and post test scores revealed significantly higher MCQ and OSCE scores for task based learning. Tutorial group also showed significant improvement in the pre and post test scores. Task based learning strategy could be used for many other topics are likely to be encountered by the students during clinical attachments. Small group teaching can include task based learning over tutorials to provide early clinical exposure in medical schools.</i></p>

Introduction

Preclinical learning provides foundation for clinical practice but is often spent in isolation from the clinics. Basic science data, when provided without context, is not utilized in diagnostic thinking¹⁴ and it is important that curriculum designers continuously develop tools and techniques which integrate clinical skills and basic sciences⁹. Rigid compartmentalization of preclinical from clinical subjects prevents learners from interacting with the patients until the second year of medical school¹⁰. Students who do not routinely interact with patients in their preclinical period have limited clinical reasoning skills. When these students enter clinics they can potentially endanger the patients with whom they work⁴. Limited clinical exposure programs in the preclinical medical curriculum curbs the enthusiasm of learners and develops negativity towards clinical learning².

Collaboration between the preclinical and clinical departments is essential to develop an integrated approach towards medical instruction. Learning strategies that focus on interlinking theory with practice and those that show importance of basic science knowledge in the clinical context are encouraged¹⁵. Early clinical exposure (ECE) is a strategy that aims at introducing the learners to patient interactions in the first year of medical school. ECE allows the learners to understand the relevance of basic science education in diagnosis, patient care, and treatment. In addition to this, when the learners relate to experiences of patients it encourages them to identify that ethics, professionalism and behaviour are equally integral in physician-patient relationship¹. This heightens the enthusiasm of students towards clinical learning from the first year of medical school² and allows them to build on their existing knowledge when they eventually enter the clinics.

The Medical Council of India (MCI) (replaced by “National Medical Commission” in 2020) introduced “Competency based undergraduate medical education curriculum-CBME” in the year 2019–20^{11,12} and has mandated early clinical exposure programs in the preclinical education. ECE programs like community visits, hospital visits including shadowing the doctor, visit to blood bank etc are greatly encouraged and implemented in several medical schools^{16,18}. However, with large patient numbers, low physician-to-patient ratios, and high population of medical students, the planning and management of such endeavours are daunting⁴. Other ECE strategies like problem based learning, case based learning and case based discussion are text or video based and they provide opportunity to acquire in-depth knowledge, facilitates team work and clinical reasoning but does not allow the students to hone clinical examination skills³. High technology simulations allow this to great extent but virtual patient interactions are resource intensive, and the more economically feasible programs do not show real signs and symptoms⁴. Preclinical task based learning (TskBL) is an early clinical exposure strategy which focuses on real tasks done by a doctor using a standardized patient encounter. The students achieve the learning objectives while undergoing the rich learning experience of simulated clinical environment. The objective of introducing this strategy was to facilitate basic and in-depth depth knowledge of various processes while developing a wide range of essential skills and attitude^{13,17}. The aim of this article is to present the effectiveness of standardized patient encounter in an early clinical exposure program using task based learning strategy in preclinical education. To achieve this aim, TskBL module for ‘diabetes mellitus’ was planned, implemented and evaluated among the first year medical students.

Method

Planning of preclinical task based learning

Preclinical task based learning strategy needed thorough planning and preparation of the modules in advance. With this aim, the following steps were taken in the planning phase.

Defining the role of team members

The first step that was carried out in planning the task based learning strategy was to specify the role of each team member. Our project included an interdisciplinary team of physiologists, doctors from department of general medicine and faculty of department of medical education. Expressing clarity about the roles and responsibilities of each team member was fundamental in planning the module. The Physiologists initiated team meetings, prepared the module and facilitated the implementation, assessment and evaluation of the module. The doctors of department of general medicine reviewed the study guides prepared and provided expert inputs on the signs and symptoms of the disease, details regarding history taking, focused physical examination and/or analysis of lab reports relevant to the patient’s history and details about patient education relevant to the diabetic patient. The faculty of department of medical education supervised each process throughout the duration of the study and provided inputs on mode of implementation, assessment and evaluation.

Defining aims and objectives of the preclinical program

The learning outcomes and student learning objectives for the first year medical program were listed under three domains: knowledge (cognitive), skill (psychomotor) and attitude (affective). This step helped in gaining insights that were relevant and useful to lay the foundation for determining the learning objectives for the specific tasks in preclinical TskBL program for the topic diabetes mellitus.

Faculty Training

A faculty development program for orientation to TskBL was conducted. The training was provided for the duration of two hours for sixteen faculty belonging to department of Physiology. The objectives of the orientation program were as follows.

At the end of the training program the faculty should be able to

1. Explain the role of TskBL in preclinical medical education
2. Explain the flow of events during planning of TskBL strategy
3. Explain the flow of events during implementation of TskBL strategy, to understand the role of faculty in TskBL
4. Explain the role of standardized patient in TskBL
5. Explain the role of students in TskBL strategy
6. Explain the usefulness of TskBL in preclinical setting
7. Facilitate the preclinical TskBL program for the given task.

After the training was complete the faculty were eligible to become facilitators during TskBL implementation.

Preparation of study guides

Direction is essential to maximise the learning round the tasks. The study guides ensure proper guidance and communication. A study guide can be a remarkable tool in TskBL⁵. It is helpful to learner, facilitator and the standardized patient. The guide contains essential instructions and the pre-requisites essential for the TskBL. Three study guides- A student study guide, a tutor study guide and a standardized patient guide were prepared. All the study guides were reviewed by faculty belonging to department of medicine. They were provided to the participants after necessary changes were made.

- Student study guide :This was provided to the students to familiarise them with the pre-reading materials , specific learning objectives, timeline and sequence of events in TskBL.
- Tutor study guide: This had information about the role of facilitator in TskBL, specific learning objectives, timeline, sequence of events in TskBL, particulars of the case, questions to be asked during mini-quiz, instructions for development of generic transferable skills through role play, details of other similar cases and information for the debriefing session.
- Standardized patient guide: This guide contained the opening statement, patient demographics, agenda, behaviour and a detailed case history.

Introducing students to the TskBL program

TskBL program was new to the students. An introduction program on TskBL was conducted for the students. In this session the students were instructed about the following

- Educational objectives in TskBL program
- Rationale for TskBL program
- Key elements and processes in TskBL program
- Role of students in TskBL program and how to use their roles effectively
- How to use learning resources effectively for self-directed learning

Training standardized patients

Individuals who are trained to exhibit the signs and symptoms of disease conditions similar to how they present in the real patients are called as standardized patients. They provide learners with an opportunity to work in a real life scenario and to practice their knowledge and skills in a safe manner⁷. In this study, two standardized patients were assigned for each task. They were trained by the faculty facilitators using standardized patient guides. These standardized patients were trained for the duration of one hour, two days a week for four weeks timeline.

Implementation of preclinical task based learning

TskBL program is implemented in two sessions: standardized patient encounter and discussion. Both sessions had a group of fourteen students and were guided by a faculty facilitator. Both the session had a similar topic. For example when TskBL group underwent TskBL on chest pain. The tutorial group underwent tutorials on myocardial infarction.

Session I

Session I took place for the duration of one hour. During this session , a team of students encountered a standardized patient. The session started with students volunteering to become a leader, a time keeper and a scribe. The team then elicited history from the standardized patient. In the next step, they analysed laboratory reports relevant to the patient's history. This session ended with patient education where students provided details about the patient's condition. Using all the information from the above task the students prepared a sequential case summary.

Session II

The second session took place after one week of session I. This duration allowed the students to prepare for session II. The student study guides was helpful to the students during this period. Session II started with presentation of sequential case summary by the students. This was followed by discussion of learning objectives. After this the learners underwent mini-quiz in which they answered the case based questions posed by the facilitator. Other similar cases were discussed (example: In diabetes mellitus the patient complains of polyuria. This complaint could also be seen in other conditions like diabetes insipidus). This was followed by development of generic skills facilitated through role play. The facilitator highlighted the key points and summarised. Session II ended with debriefing session in which the facilitator motivated the students to reflect on their performance in session I and session II. Facilitator feedback and Standardized patient feedback related to learners performance on history taking, clinical examination and patient education, communication skills, group dynamics and their attitude as a healthcare provider were also provided. The tutor study guides provided the framework to guide the facilitator in every step of TskBL. Session II took place for the duration of two hours.

Role of faculty

The role of faculty in TskBL session I is that of a moderator. This is similar to the role of the facilitator in brainstorming session of problem based learning (PBL). The facilitator encouraged the learners to actively participate in standardised patient encounter. They also provided direction to the participants to complete all the processes in an effective and timely manner. They recorded their feedback related to history taking, physical examination and patient education.

In session II of TskBL, the facilitator encouraged the students to engage in discussion and boosted the development of generic skills like patient education through mode of role play. They highlighted the vital issues, summarised the task and discussed other similar cases. During debriefing, the facilitator encouraged the students to reflect on their own performance. They also provided feedback to the students regarding their performance in session I and session II.

Assessment of preclinical task based learning

Assessment is critical in learning. The Assessment reflected the aims objectives and contents of the module. Formative and summative assessment were employed.

Formative assessment

Formative assessment was done using task end grades. This was accomplished using facilitator feedback and standardized patient feedback. The feedback was recorded and provided to the participating teams in the form of a checklist. The formative feedback was provided for groups performance and individual scores were not provided. Assessment was done as per the rubrics given. The assessor observed the students perform and graded the students according to the rubrics. It consisted of grids containing procedures to be performed and its interpretation for each task. The facilitators and standardized patients graded the groups performance using a three point scale in which point 1= below expectation, point 2= meets expectation and point 3= exceeds expectation to assess student's participation in standardized patient encounter (session I) and their performance during discussion session (session II). An explanation about what qualifies as below, meets and above expectation was provided for each procedure. They assessors also wrote down comments on what was done best and what needed improvement.

The facilitator checklist contained feedback on the group's performance associated with history taking, clinical examination, patient education, communication skills, group dynamics and their attitude as a healthcare provider. The standardized patient feedback contained feedback on Patient doctor interaction, Eliciting history, physical examination and patient education.

Summative assessment

Summative assessment was done using a multiple choice question (MCQ) test and objective structured clinical exam (OSCE).

Multiple choice question (MCQ) test

MCQ test was conducted to assess the knowledge. The test consisted of ten higher order case based MCQs which tested clinical reasoning. The questions were focussed at the “know how” level of the Miller’s pyramid. Ten questions were to be answered in ten minutes duration. There was no negative scoring and each correctly answered question was awarded one mark. Maximum score that could be obtained in the MCQ test was ten and minimum score was zero. The individual scores of the learners for MCQ test was recorded.

Objective structured clinical exam (OSCE)

Skills and attitude were assessed using OSCE. Two OSCE stations appropriate to the task of ten marks each were considered for each task. Example- providing relevant information about the patient’s condition (diabetes mellitus) to the standardized patient. Maximum score that could be obtained in OSCE was twenty and minimum score was zero. The individual test scores of the learners for OSCE was recorded.

Tutorials

The conventional small group learning method that was routinely used is tutorials. In this module, a group of 28 students were guided by one facilitator. The tutorial module consisted of one session and took place for two hours duration. This session started with team formation. The students worked in smaller groups of 5-6 students each. Case based questions were provided to the students by the facilitator. The students discussed in their respective groups and answered the questions. This discussion was guided by the facilitator. At the end of the tutorial, the facilitator discussed the answers, clarified the doubts and provided feedback. The questions employed in the tutorial session was similar to those used during mini-quiz of TskBL modules.

Role of faculty

The role of faculty in tutorial learning was that of a facilitator. The facilitator ensured that every student participated in discussion. The facilitator provided guidance regarding the subject at hand while encouraging the students to discuss. They probed the students to think in the right direction. They discussed the answers and clarified the doubts. At the end of the tutorial session they provided constructive feedback regarding the specific learning objectives and team’s performance related to group dynamics and team work

Procedures

Study design and setting

This is a non-equivalent group design quasi experimental study. Non-random (convenience) sampling was employed. Randomisation of participants into the TskBL group and Tutorial group was achieved by student allotment to small group learning in various batches allotted by the preclinical department student posting process which was unrelated to the TskBL or tutorial learning.

Sample size and grouping

The study subjects were first year medical students studying in Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore. They (n=250) were divided into three groups. Group A consisted of 84 students, group B consisted of 84 students and group C consisted of 82 students. Group A was TskBL group (n=84). Group B and group C were in the conventional learning (n=166) group.

The TskBL group (n=84/n=82) was further divided into six small TskBL groups. Each small TskBL group had fourteen students and was guided by one facilitator. The conventional learning group (n=166) was further divided into six tutorial groups. Each tutorial group had 27-28 students and was guided by one facilitator.

Both groups attended the theory classes in physiology, practical sessions and clinical examinations concerning the tasks before the commencement of task based learning/tutorial sessions. Following this, the students of TskBL group underwent TskBL as described above. The students in the control group underwent conventional learning method of tutorials.

Ethical considerations

The study was approved by Institutional ethics committee of Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore (IEC KMC MLR 04-17/77). Only those students who volunteered to participate were included in the study.

Data analysis

Unpaired t-test was applied to compare the mean scores of control group and TskBL group. Paired t-test was applied to compare the pretest and post test values of control group and the TskBL group. All the results were expressed as mean (standard deviation) and $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Results and Discussion

(Table1) Gives the comparison of MCQ and OSCE scores of tutorial group and TskBL groups. The mean MCQ and OSCE scores of the TskBL group was significantly higher than for the tutorial group. and in the OSCE. The tutorial group also had a significant improvement in both MCQ and OSCE scores.

Table 1. Comparison of mean scores of tutorial and TskBL group

Variables	Tutorial	TskBL	P value
MCQ	6.22 (1.38)	7.00 (1.48)	<0.001***
OSCE	12.93 (2.32)	15.23 (1.53)	<0.001***

Results are reported as mean (standard deviation). $N = 166$ students for tutorial group and 84 for TskBL group. P value: * $P < 0.05$. ** $P < 0.01$. *** $P < 0.001$.

When the pretest and post test scores were compared between the tutorial and TskBL methods in (Table12) students performed better after TskBL in both the MCQ test

Variable	Tutorial		P value	TskBL		P value
	Pre	Post		Pre	Post	
MCQ	4.79 (1.43)	6.22 (1.38)	<0.001 ***	4.77 (1.76)	7.00 (1.48)	<0.001 ***
OSCE	11.86 (1.29)	12.93 (2.32)	<0.001 ***	11.69 (1.24)	15.23 (1.53)	<0.001 ***

Table 2. Comparison of pretest and post-test scores

Results are reported as mean (standard deviation). $N = 166$ students for tutorial group and 84 for TskBL group. P value: * $P < 0.05$. ** $P < 0.01$. *** $P < 0.001$.

This study employed comparison two small group teaching modules, TskBL and tutorial learning. The results show that TskBL helped in development of knowledge of diabetes mellitus while aiding development of wide array of skills, attitudes and behaviour among preclinical students. TskBL led to improvement in knowledge which was reflected in MCQ scores. The improvement in skills and attitude was reflected in OSCE. Both the scores were significantly higher when compared with the conventional procedure of tutorials.

The higher scores in TskBL may be because in TskBL module the learners underwent standardized patient encounter in which they not only discussed the learning issues but also practiced the essential skills used for summative assessment. This is particularly true for improvement in OSCE scores in the TskBL group. However, the tutorial group mainly focussed on acquisition of knowledge and less importance was given for skill development. The TskBL group also had less number of students in each group and they invested more time in learning about diabetes mellitus (two sessions). An equal and impartial experience was not provided in terms of number of students, time duration and providing formative feedback. The tutorial group had greater student size and consisted of one session of two hours duration. In comparison the TskBL group had smaller group and was of three hours durations (two sessions). The TskBL group received more detailed feedback as compared to the tutorial team.

The routinely employed small group teaching strategy was tutorials. This is conventionally practiced across various medical colleges as it provides an active learning environment and is easy to execute⁸. While tutorial learning improved learning it was less productive when compared to TskBL. This may be because tutorial learning focused predominantly on gaining knowledge and when basic science knowledge is provided without context, is not helpful in clinical reasoning¹⁴.

Many medical schools have taken up TskBL module for undergraduate medical education in the clinical years. A research conducted in the International Medical University among undergraduate students in clinical setting reported beneficial effect of TskBL on interpersonal communication¹⁷. TskBL was used as the foundation for integration and problem-based learning in the clinical period of Dundee curriculum⁶.

The perceptions of the learners regarding TskBL module were not reported in the current study, but during TskBL the students appeared interested about the clinical implications and importance of diabetes mellitus. This may be attributed to the standardized patient encounter, which is recognised to improve diagnostic thinking, practice and skills essential in the preclinical education⁴.

Conclusion

TskBL is a detailed and structured small group learning module that provides early clinical exposure. During the standardized patient encounter and the discussion session several in which details of diabetes mellitus was fused with acquisition of communication skills, interpersonal relation, behaviour as a doctor, patient-physician relationship and soft skills like compassion. In our study, TskBL was planned and implemented for the topic diabetes mellitus. This strategy can be implemented for several other topics that are regularly encountered in the clinics. even-though it needs investment of additional time and manpower this strategy can be preferred over tutorials as it contributes to overall development of preclinical learners.

Recommendations

The researchers made the following recommendations:

- Implementation of TskBL modules for other topics that are routinely encountered in clinical practice.
- Conduct studies on evaluation of TskBL strategy using focus group discussion.

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Author Information

Roopashree Shenoy

Department of Physiology
Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore
Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal,
India

Animesh Jain

Department of Community Medicine
Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore
Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal,
India

Bhagyalakshmi K

Department of Physiology
Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore
Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal,
India

Arun Shirali

Department of Medicine
Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore
Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal,
India

Sneha B Shetty

Department of Physiology
Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore
Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal,
India

Anand Ramakrishna

Department of Pulmonary Medicine
Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore
Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal,
India

Rashmi K S

Department of Physiology
Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore
Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal,
India
